

STUDY OF THE POLYMORPHOUS TRANSFORMATION OF QUARTZ JERDANAK FIELD

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Pure crystalline silica at normal pressure experiences at upon heating, structural transformations according to the scheme: α -quartz $\leftrightarrow$ β -quartz $\rightarrow$ β -cristobalite and at subsequent cooling - β -cristobalite $\leftrightarrow$ α -cristobalite [1]. However, strictly speaking, in In a number of cases (in particular, for grains of rock crystal), this scheme practically remains only one transformation before the moment of melting, namely α -quartz $\leftrightarrow$ β -quartz. In others cases, in the presence of a sufficient amount of modifier impurities, it is observed process of formation of β -tridymite (T=870°C). In addition, the thermal structural diagram transformations of crystalline silica can largely depend on its granulometric composition and heat treatment modes (heating speed, time excerpts, etc.). In this regard, in the practice of producing transparent quartz glass from natural quartz, for each specific type of raw material, its own modes are developed heat treatment.

The purpose of this study is to examine some of the features thermal structural polymorphic transformations of quartzite deposit "Jerdanak".

Analyzed result

Sample Information

Sample name Umar Ch. 5
File name Umar Ch. 5
Application Unamuy
Date 2021/3/4 10:55
Analyzed by
Counts 1
Comment

Analyzed result(FP method, Scatter)

No.	Component	Result	Unit	Stat. Err.	LLD	LLQ
1	Cl	0.0397	mass%	0.0004	0.0001	0.0003
2	Br	0.0003	mass%	<0.0001	<0.0001	0.0001
3	Al2O3	7.13	mass%	0.0190	0.0251	0.0753
4	SiO2	90.0	mass%	0.0220	0.111	0.332
5	SO3	0.0376	mass%	0.0008	0.0005	0.0014
6	K2O	1.49	mass%	0.0092	0.0029	0.0088
7	CaO	0.0399	mass%	0.0022	0.0052	0.0156
8	TiO2	0.0664	mass%	0.0011	0.0009	0.0026
9	V2O5 (0.0020)	0.0020	mass%	0.0004	0.0011	0.0034
10	Cr2O3 (0.0007)	0.0007	mass%	0.0001	0.0003	0.0010
11	MnO	0.0062	mass%	0.0004	0.0008	0.0023
12	Fe2O3	0.0659	mass%	0.0009	0.0006	0.0017
13	CuO	0.0020	mass%	0.0001	0.0002	0.0005
14	ZnO	0.0012	mass%	<0.0001	<0.0001	0.0004
15	Ga2O3	0.0019	mass%	<0.0001	<0.0001	0.0003
16	GeO2	0.0006	mass%	<0.0001	<0.0001	0.0003
17	Rb2O	0.0057	mass%	<0.0001	<0.0001	0.0001
18	SnO	0.0020	mass%	<0.0001	<0.0001	0.0001
19	Y2O3	0.0023	mass%	<0.0001	<0.0001	0.0003
20	ZrO2	0.116	mass%	0.0010	0.0003	0.0010
21	Nb2O5	0.0021	mass%	0.0002	0.0003	0.0008
22	Ag2O	0.0005	mass%	<0.0001	0.0001	0.0004
23	PbO	0.0006	mass%	<0.0001	0.0001	0.0004
24	U3O8	0.0006	mass%	<0.0001	0.0002	0.0006

Analyzed result

Sample Information

Sample name Umar Ch. 9
File name Umar Ch. 9
Application Unamuy
Date 2021/3/4 11:37
Analyzed by
Counts 1
Comment

Analyzed result(FP method, Scatter)

No.	Component	Result	Unit	Stat. Err.	LLD	LLQ
1	Cl	0.0483	mass%	0.0004	0.0001	0.0003
2	Br	0.0003	mass%	<0.0001	<0.0001	0.0001
3	Al2O3	4.20	mass%	0.0166	0.0258	0.0775
4	SiO2	94.3	mass%	0.0219	0.114	0.343
5	SO3	0.0501	mass%	0.0010	0.0005	0.0015
6	K2O	0.801	mass%	0.0068	0.0020	0.0061
7	CaO	0.0225	mass%	0.0017	0.0042	0.0126
8	TiO2	0.0395	mass%	0.0009	0.0008	0.0024
9	Fe2O3	0.0347	mass%	0.0007	0.0006	0.0017
10	CuO	0.0017	mass%	<0.0001	0.0002	0.0005
11	Ga2O3	0.0014	mass%	<0.0001	0.0001	0.0003
12	As2O3	0.0003	mass%	<0.0001	<0.0001	0.0002
13	Rb2O	0.0031	mass%	<0.0001	<0.0001	0.0001
14	SrO	0.0014	mass%	<0.0001	<0.0001	0.0002
15	Y2O3	0.0017	mass%	<0.0001	<0.0001	0.0003
16	ZrO2	0.130	mass%	0.0010	0.0003	0.0010
17	Ag2O	0.0008	mass%	<0.0001	0.0001	0.0004
18	SnO2	0.0024	mass%	0.0001	0.0003	0.0009
19	GeO2	0.0018	mass%	0.0001	0.0003	0.0009
20	OsO4 (0.0008)	0.0001	mass%	0.0001	0.0004	0.0011

Spectrum

a)

Spectrum

b)

Picture 1. Chemical composition of quartzite. a- not cleaned, b-cleaned.

As can be seen from Picture 1, the content of iron oxide decreases as a result enrichment of the original quartzite from 0.065-0.034%. The aluminum oxide content decreases from 7.13-4.20%. Enrichment was carried out using the wet method. Large pieces for this crushed and washed with water, then the samples in the form of tablets were molded semi-dry method. After molding, samples of the original quartzite were subjected to modification heat treatment. The studies were carried out in an electric furnace with heating elements made of silicon carbide in an air atmosphere. Heat treatment temperature 573–1450°C, (Fig. 1b,c,d) time spent in the oven at maximum temperature 1-2 hours, grain size of the original quartz corresponded to the class +10-50 mm.

Picture 2. Natural quartzite.

Picture 3. Fired quartzite at 573-640°C with hardening

Picture 4. fired quartzite at 1430°C with sharp quenching in cold water.

Picture 4. Fired quartzite at 1430°C. 2 hours with slow cooling X-ray images of samples.

a) original quartzite from the Jerdanak deposit; b) fired quartz at 573-640°C. c) burned quartz at 1430°C with sharp quenching for 2 hours in cold water; d) burnt quartz at 1430°C. at slow cooling down.

The diffraction pattern of the original quartzite (Pic 1.) showed the presence of reflections of quartz a diffraction pattern of a sample obtained by firing at 573-640 °C and with sharp cooling at water, the presence of the main phase was discovered - low-temperature α - quartz, in (Pic. 2).

The quality of the final product was assessed by the yield of cristobalite. For subsequent During the research, cristobalite samples were taken, the yield of

which was at least 39.5%. Quality control of cristobalite was carried out on an X-ray diffractometer XRD filter, Ni, 1.54178 tube current and voltage mode 30 mA, 30 kV) and constant speed detector rotation 4 degrees/min in increments of 0.02 degrees. ($u/2\theta$ -clutch), and the scanning angle varied from 4 to 80°. (Fig. 1). The fired samples were subjected to sharp quenching in cold water and slow cooling in the oven. (Pic. 3). X-ray diffraction pattern of a sample obtained with firing at 1430 °C for 2 hours, and upon sharp cooling in water showed that reflexes correspond to the main phase quartz-60.5% and high-temperature cristobalite-30.5%, a (Pic. 4) diffraction pattern of a sample fired to 1430 °C, and with slow cooling in the furnace showed the presence of the main phase of quartz - 81.4% and high-temperature cristobalite - 18.6%. Studies have shown that with sudden cooling in water, the degree cristobolitization increases than with slow cooling, which indicates possibilities of using quartzite from the Jerdanak deposit for production dinas brick and glazes for porcelain.

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